

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: broiler

Level: slaughter

Keywords: physiology

Background context provided by the requestor

The query is part of a discussion we are having with the poultry chain, where we aim to implement measures to improve the welfare of broiler before slaughter.

Question raised by the requestor

Is there any information available on the time it takes to empty the crop and the stomach of poultry after feed withdrawal, and are there any factors that may influence this time?

Answer

• Introduction

At the end of the rearing period, broilers are transported in containers to the slaughterhouse. They are usually deprived of feed for a period before being caught and crated. Feed withdrawal is practiced to allow time for the digestive system to empty before processing, leaving less ingesta and faeces that potentially could cause carcass contamination (Caffrey et al., 2017). Due to this routine practice known as fasting, broilers may experience prolonged hunger, affecting their welfare. The duration of feed withdrawal will depend on journey time, but should not exceed 12 h in the EU member states as the European legislation (COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2007/43/EC) requires that "Feed shall be either continuously available or be meal fed and **must not be withdrawn from chickens more than 12 hours before the expected slaughter time**". Within this 12 h period, several factors may influence the time required to empty the birds' digestive system. This document describes, based on the existing literature, the time needed to empty the different parts of the gastrointestinal tract, the duration of feed withdrawal required to reduce contamination risks, the factors affecting both the rate of emptying and contamination, and the welfare consequences of feed deprivation for the birds.

• How long does it take to empty the gastrointestinal tract?

This answer will be based on the following assumptions.

- It concerns the time from last feed enters the mouth to the time this feed is excreted from the cloaca.
- The focus will be on the entire gastrointestinal tract, also known as the "gut". Including the crop, proventriculus (glandular stomach), gizzard (muscular stomach), small intestine, ceca, colon, and rectum.
- Some of the studies on fasting time include transport and waiting time. Any transport/waiting time is added as '+xx h' to the fasting time.

Crop

The crop is a storage organ, which can contain a large amount of feed before continuing to the stomach. The storage capacity depends on training of the organ to be used and can be dependent on light or feed programmes. For example, broilers fed *ad libitum* will have lower crop capacity than those that are meal-fed (i.e., involving periods in between

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meals with no access to feed for which feed has to be stored) (Svihus, 2014). Being the first digestive segment, it is quicker to empty than the remaining compartments of the gut. Kim et al. (2007) found that the crop content in broilers was close to empty at 6 + 1.5 h of fasting (0.57 g) whereas the content at 0 + 1.5 h was 12.57 g. At 9 + 1.5 h, the crop was essentially empty with only 0.05 g of content on average. Warriss et al. (2004) found a maximal clearance rate at 4 h of fasting. Both studies found great variation of crop content between individuals at all fasting times (Kim et al., 2007, Warriss et al., 2004). These commercial broilers from 2004 and 2007 have most likely been older when sent to slaughter compared to the 33-day-old broilers from 2014, which Svihus (2014) states do not use their crop considerably. The hybrid, feed and age effects will be discussed more deeply in Section 4.

Proventriculus

The proventriculus has a lower feed capacity compared to the crop, being a small and short part of the gut (Svihus, 2014). Its clearance is therefore of little interest, though it has been found to have a quick response to fasting. Kim et al. (2007) found a lower proventriculus content at the first timepoint after fasting, i.e., at 4 + 1.5 h a reduction from 1.15 g to 0.52 g was found.

Gizzard

The gizzard has a higher capacity to hold feed than the proventriculus and is therefore more important for total gut content. In the study by Kim et al. (2007), the gizzard content was lower at 6 + 1.5 h compared to 0 + 1.5 h (14.49 vs. 19.68 g). They did not find it completely emptied like the crop, the last time point being at 12 + 1.5 h (containing 11.5 g of content). This could be a result of the presence of grit; stones present which assist the mechanical digestion occurring in the gizzard (Svihus, 2014).

In a study by Xue et al. (2021) an effect on content compared to 0 + 4 h was not found until 10 + 4 h of fasting (10.98 g vs 3.50 g). A numerical reduction from 10.92 g to 6.87 g was found between 4 + 4 h and 6 + 4 h. It must be noted that this was a study with male Arbor Acres broilers at 53 days-of-age which could slow the clearance of intestinal content compared to fast-growing broilers (see Section 4).

Small intestines

Like the crop, the small intestine can contain large amounts of feed, but the feed will not bypass this segment like it occasionally does with the crop. Poultry has an extremely short colon compared to other species, causing the small intestines to be the segment holding the most intestinal content. Kim et al. (2007) found a quick reduction of content during feed withdrawal. At 3 + 1.5 h it had decreased from 36.04 to 12.71 g compared to 0 + 1.5. Similarly, Xue et al. (2021) found that the small intestine content was reduced from 32.25 g to 18.04 g between 0 + 4 h and 4 + 4 h. At the longest fasting time of 10 + 4 h, the small intestine content was 3.50 g.

Caeca

Kim et al. (2007) found that fasting 0, 3, 6, 8 or 12 h before a 1.5 h transport had no effect on the caecal content in industry broilers. This is not surprising considering the mechanic of the caeca which excretes content independently and sporadically two-three times a day (Svihus, 2014).

Colon and rectum

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The colon and rectum only contain small amounts of content like the proventriculus (Svihus, 2014). Kim et al. (2007) found a level of 0.58-0.78 g intestinal content in the rectum ranging from a fasting period of 0 + 1.5 h to 12 + 1.5 h. There were no significant differences, which is not surprising as it contains such a small amount of content that complete clearance is difficult to reach.

General estimate of entire gut

Some studies have assessed total content of the gut. Gomes et al. (2008) found that the total content of the gut was minimized when broilers fasted between 9 and 10 hours. Warriss et al. (2004) found a plateau in total gut contents at 8 h of fasting where the contents were minimized to 32 g compared to 122 g in the group that had not been fasted. At 24 hours of fasting the total content was at an average of 34 g.

To conclude, a 6 h total feed withdrawal reduces content in crop and small intestines substantially, but a margin of 2-4 h should be added to ensure clearance of these segments. These two digestive segments have a much higher content compared to the proventriculus, colon, and rectum. This estimate does not include the ceca, which empty sporadically during the day. There is, to the knowledge of the authors, no studies where the gut is concluded to be completely empty at a certain time point, and from the existing studies, it can be concluded that the complete gut will not be empty within a time span of 24 h.

There is a lack of recent studies on the emptying of the gut, which is unfortunate as genetics, management and feeding strategies have changed as well as the age at slaughter which has been decreasing in the last decades. None of the studies above have been on broilers of less than 42 days of age. In Section 4, this point will be discussed. Indeed, the less developed gut will most likely empty at a higher rate. For European Chicken Commitment-certified or similar certified broilers the estimated fasting time for emptying the gut can be assumed to be a better fit due to a higher age at slaughter.

1. How long should feed withdrawal last to reduce carcass contamination risk?

Section 2 focused on the issue of the gut being emptied, but an important question is whether there will be contamination of carcass on the slaughter line due to faecal material. Contamination is when faecal matter spills at the evisceration and thereby contaminates the carcass. This is important for the food safety of the final product and is therefore also a point of concern for the slaughterhouses. Several studies have found similar tendencies with contamination risk decreasing with fasting for 10-12 h and then increasing once more after 13-14 h.

The increasing risk at fasting times of 13-14 h is a result of the tissue becoming frail and thereby being in higher risk of bursting during handling of the carcass (Zuidhof et al., 2004b, Brizio et al., 2015). The contamination risk is further increased due to a higher shedding of enterobacteria such as Salmonella and Campylobacter when fasting for a long period of time (Bilgili, 2002).

A long fasting and transit, 16 + 12 h, resulted in more contamination compared to 8 h fasting followed by either 4 or 8 h transit (Zuidhof et al., 2004b) for 42-day-old broilers, so 28 h compared to 12 and 16 h in total. A longer fasting time will also increase the amount of excreta not derived from feed, i.e., residue of degenerating intestinal cells, which increase viscosity of the faeces (Gomes et al., 2008).

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Brizio et al. (2015) found that fasting 7, 9, 11, 13 or 15 h had no significant effect on the visual faecal contamination at the evisceration line in a commercial slaughterhouse. In a review, Bilgili (2002) argued that 6-7 h of fasting will result in full guts and higher contamination risk during evisceration compared to longer fasting periods. On the other end, feed withdrawal periods exceeding 13-14 h may also increase contamination risk at slaughter (Bilgili, 2002).

A noticeable reduction of contamination occurred between fasting times of 8 and 12 h in a study by Zuidhof et al. (2004a) while there was no increase again between hours 12 and 16 as shown in other papers. This is a longer fasting to reduce contamination than the one reported needed in a study by Wabeck (1972) where the maximum reduction in visual contamination of the carcass was found at 10 hours, and at 14 and 24 h of fasting, the contamination of increased again.

These findings suggests that there is an optimal window of feed withdrawal time of 10-12 h for lowering contamination risk at slaughter. Short feed withdrawal periods leave more content in the gut which might spill at the slaughter line while prolonged feed withdrawal periods increase risk of rupture of tissue.

2. Which factors influence the speed of emptying the gut and carcass contamination risk

Below is some of the factors which can affect the emptying of the gut and/or the carcass contamination risk at slaughter.

Transport

Zuidhof et al. (2004a) found that there is no difference between being in stationary crates and being transported in crates but concluded that this was not in accordance with other studies. There is unfortunately a lack of recent studies where the birds are fasted, crated and euthanized on-site compared to transported and the effect on gut emptying or carcass contamination.

Age

The larger the digestive tract, the longer feed will take to pass through the system (Svihus, 2014). Therefore, broiler age will increase the time it takes for the gut to empty. This must be kept in mind when applying older studies which are most likely using broilers that were slaughtered at older ages than current practice. So, as mentioned in Section 2, the older studies are most likely on broilers with slower passage of feed through the gut.

Hybrids

There is, to knowledge of the authors, no studies directly comparing passage of feed during pre-slaughter feed deprivation between hybrids. However, there might be differences between hybrids due to the age at slaughter being different across the genotypes.

Light

Ramao et al. (2011) found no difference on speed of emptying the gut when fasting at light intensities of 5 and 20 lux, however performing feed withdrawal during the scotoperiod will reduce the speed of emptying the gut (May et al., 1990). At 2 h, 4 h and 6 h of feed withdrawal during the photoperiod, the crop content was 12.8, 4.2 and 0.5 g, respectively, while fasting for similar durations during the scotoperiod resulted in 25.1, 10.5 and 3.3 g of crop content, respectively.

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Coarse feed materials and intermittent feeding

When broilers are provided with a coarser diet, their digestive tract will grow more compared to a fine diet (Svihus, 2014). Like for a more mature gut, this will result in a slower passage of feed through the gut. This means that broilers with access to roughage or outdoor areas with vegetation will need more time to pass the digesta.

Xue et al. (2021) found a faster emptying of the small intestines for the indoor reared Arbor Acres broilers compared to broilers from the same batch but with outdoor access. Interestingly, the contamination propensity scale, i.e., an assessment of the volume of faeces exiting the dead bird when providing pressure on abdomen, did not differ between the indoor and outdoor groups.

Intermittent feeding encourages use of the crop, resulting in increased duration of feed in the system. Svihus (2014) found that broilers having feed access twice a day still had feed in the crop 5 h after last feeding compared to the *ad libitum* group (10 g vs. the 40 g at 1 h fasting) whereas the *ad libitum* fed had little to no content.

Water

According to Zuidhof et al. (2004a), water access during feed withdrawal will increase the contamination at the evisceration, but other studies have found no effect of water access during feed withdrawal on gut content in birds fasted for up to 12 h (Gomes et al., 2008, May and Deaton, 1989). Warriss et al. (2004) found that providing water during feed withdrawal did not result in a change in the number of defaecations between time points during periods ranging from 4, 8, 12, 16, 20 and 24 h while the group without feed nor water had a significant decrease as duration of fasting increased (Warriss et al., 2004). As for the content of the gut, the group with water had more content in the gut compared to the no-water group (53 g vs. 37 g) even though the digesta was not more wet (Warriss et al., 2004). The water content of the gut content was not significantly different between the water or no water access groups at any other segment than the gizzard. This result is in disagreement with Leeson et al. (1992) who found a higher clearance of the gut when giving access to water during fasting.

To conclude, studies on the effects of removing water during feed withdrawal have inconsistent results. Some find no effect (Gomes et al., 2008, May and Deaton, 1989), some find decreased gut content when water is not provided (Warriss et al., 2004), and some find an improved clearance when providing water access (Leeson et al., 1992).

3. Welfare consequences of feed withdrawal

Depending on the duration of feed withdrawal, birds' strain and age, body condition, ambient temperature, and additional stressors during transport, fasting may lead to welfare consequences associated with prolonged hunger, as metabolic requirements are no longer met. Broilers being birds with high metabolism and having free access to feed on farm are at particular risk of experiencing prolonged hunger (EFSA, 2022). Glycogen reserves are very small in broilers. According to studies, deprivation of feed for 6 h results in depletion of glycogen stores in the liver of broilers (Warriss et al., 1988; Savenije et al., 2002), causing prolonged hunger to be experienced (Knowles et al., 1995). This will increase with time, exacerbating the impact on birds' welfare.

Broilers are highly motivated to feed (Weeks et al., 2000). Feed withdrawal therefore disrupts normal behaviour, and birds are likely to experience hunger as a negative affective state after a relatively short period without feed

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(EFSA, 2022). Hence, after 6 h, metabolic requirements are no longer met and so the welfare consequence of prolonged hunger starts. After 12 h, the welfare consequence of prolonged hunger is almost certain, leading to a weakened condition in the bird (EFSA, 2022). To prevent the risk of broilers experiencing prolonged hunger, the total time without feed should not exceed 6 h. In addition, broilers should have access to water until catching to prevent prolonged thirst, which may occur when birds spend considerable time in transport between loading and time of slaughter, thereby substantially increasing the total duration without water (EFSA, 2022).

Conclusions

According to literature, complete emptying of the gut of broilers pre-slaughter will not occur within 24 h of feed withdrawal. However, a substantial decrease in contents of crop, gizzard and small intestines can be accomplished within 8-10 h of fasting which includes catching, transport and lairage. Contamination risk at the slaughter line will be at its lowest around 12 h of fasting, while both shorter and longer fasting time will increase the risk of carcass contamination.

Several factors including transport, age, light, and feed can affect the time needed for feed to pass through the system. Studies on the effect of hybrids could not be found.

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